

Chinese Language

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Abstract

Being one of the oldest languages of world, Chinese language has a rich history. It has its own characteristics which are quite unique as compared to most of the other languages. Unlike the alphabetical Western and other Indo-European languages, Chinese language is a logographic writing system that makes use of symbols known as characters. An attempt has been made in this paper to gauge the major characteristics of the Chinese language. It also traces the history of the language succinctly.

Keywords: Chinese, Mandarin, characters, simplified language, etc.

While discussing Chinese culture, we have to take notice of the Chinese language and the unique Chinese writing system. The Chinese language is the oldest language in the world which has been in continuous use since the second millennium BCE. The native speakers of the Chinese language (Mandarin) are far greater than any other language in the world. The United Nations Organization (UNO) has approved Modern Standard Chinese as one of the six official languages.

The Chinese language is not a single entity but an amalgamation of many dialects or varieties having the same Chinese script. Most of them are mutually unintelligible to their respective speakers. They differ mainly in pronunciation and vocabulary. The prominent dialects are Mandarin, Cantonese, Hakka, Wu, Min, Xiang, and Gan. The official national language of China is a variety of Mandarin based on the speech in the capital Beijing. It is called as Putonghua means everyday speech. “Modern Standard Written Chinese is by and large the written form of standard spoken Chinese” (Chen 200).

The various varieties of Chinese languages had a standard literary language known as *wenyan*. This literary language has no single standard of pronunciation. The speaker of a dialect reads texts according to the rules of pronunciation of his own native dialect. Till the New Culture Movement of 1917-21, the *wenyan* was used for almost all formal writings. However, since the May Fourth Movement of 1919 the vernacular language became the main style of all kinds of formal or informal writing. It is known as *baihua*, the written form of the northern vernacular, better known by foreigners as Mandarin. The old literary or classical language disappeared from the life of common people.

The writing system developed by the Chinese is the oldest known writing system to be in continuous use. The continuity of Chinese literature for the last more than three thousand years has been mainly due to the writing system employed by the Chinese language. It might have happened due to the First Emperor, who made the Small Seal script standard throughout his empire while recognising the various dialects. Inscriptions on bones and tortoise shells found at Anyang dating back to the Shang dynasty (18th–12th centuries BCE) are the oldest extant samples of Chinese writing.

“These inscriptions are usually brief and factual and cannot be considered literature. Nonetheless, they are significant in that their sizable vocabulary (about 3,400 characters, of which nearly 2,000 have been reliably deciphered) has proved to be the direct ancestor of the modern Chinese script. Moreover, the syntactical structure of the language bears a striking resemblance to later usages.” (Li, et al.)

The famous Scottish historian John Keay commented that the in-depth study of oracle bone writing proved that “... the Shang elite was indeed literate and that the Chinese script of today is unique in being the direct descendent of one used in the second millennium BC” (43). The Chinese writing system is unique as it has been in use continuously for the last more than four thousand years, making it the most ancient writing system in the world still being in use.

In Indian and Western languages, the letters stand for sounds and the letters are combined to form words. As a result of it, there is a very close correspondence between the written and the spoken language. On the other hand, the Chinese language is very different. The Chinese language is not alphabetical like Western and other Indo-European languages,

but a logographic writing system. Instead of letters, it makes use of symbols, known as characters that indicate both sounds and meanings. The characters represent things or ideas and not sound like any alphabetical language. As a result, they do not represent a particular sound. There are thousands of characters; a character represents a single word. Chinese newspaper can be read across the country; however, they cannot understand a drama performed in a dialect.

The symbols are painted using brush and ink; thus, written Chinese has visual appeal. The art of Chinese calligraphy was born through this unique writing system and has become an indispensable part of the Chinese culture. Calligraphy has been considered as a part of fine art like painting. The written language prevents the development of entirely separate languages. However, it also makes the acquisition of basic literacy difficult because to learn basic reading and writing; one needs to learn at least one thousand characters.

In order to acquire essential fluency in written Chinese, you have to learn almost four thousand characters making it one of the most challenging languages in the world to learn. In the Chinese writing system, a specific character is used to write each meaningful syllable or the meaningless syllabic that is part of a polysyllabic word. The written Chinese language is one of the most challenging writing systems in the world. However, in order to make it easy to learn, simplified characters were introduced in 1956. Liu Yuli argues that “many of the simplifications were not new inventions, but continuations of older variant forms”. Many simplified characters have been in use for hundred of year. It replaced the classical script, which is too much difficult to learn. Though the Chinese script is used all over China, the pronunciations of characters change according to the region. Consequently, Chinese people from different regions with different dialect can communicate with each other in written form in spite of not understanding the speech of each other. Calligraphy, or drawing of characters, has become an important art in China. Writers make use of brush and black ink to write characters.

In the Chinese language ‘how you say’ something is equally important as ‘what you say’. It means tones or intonations are the primary tools in conveying the meaning as different tones distinguish words that otherwise are pronounced identically, and the Chinese language has numerous homophones. The Standard Chinese language has four basic tones.

The meaning of a word can be changed by changing the tone of voice. Depending on the tone of the speaker, the Chinese word *ma* can signify mother or horse. Though officially in most parts of China people speak Chinese, there are considerable variations in the spoken language of two different regions. In order to overcome this problem, the schools all over China teach the same variety of spoken language called as Mandarin Chinese.

Traditionally, most of the Chinese words are monosyllabic; however, since the twentieth century, polysyllabic words have gained popularity. There is no inflexion to Chinese words. A single word can be used as any parts of speech depending on its place in the sentence. Therefore, word order is quite important in Chinese. In the Chinese language, tones are mainly used to distinguish similar-looking words; on the other hand, in English tones have a grammatical function. The word order of Chinese is subject–verb–object and complement and modifier. The Modern Standard Chinese makes use of nearly 1300 to 1400 different syllables.

At the beginning of the twentieth century, through the efforts of many years, the Modern Standard Chinese language was developed. Pinyin, an official system of Romanisation, was introduced in 1956. It was based on the pronunciation of the Beijing dialect. It proved quite useful in spreading the modern Standard Chinese language which became the official system in late 1958. It is taught along with Chinese characters throughout China. Pinyin indicates the pronunciation of the Putonghua or the common speech of China.

In order to translate Chinese in Roman script, one has to reproduce its pronunciation and not the script itself. Additionally, the Roman alphabet cannot represent the tones of the Chinese language, which are essential in conveying the meaning. There have been two main transcription systems of Chinese used for Romanisation:

1. Wade-Giles
2. Pinyin

The Wade-Giles system of transcription was first introduced by Sir Thomas Francis Wade in 1859 which was improved by Herbert A, Giles. It remained the primary system of Romanisation for the next more than a hundred years. The official Chinese transcription system for Romanisation, Pinyin, was accepted in 1958, which is now almost globally accepted. It has now become the primary system of Chinese transcription. Borrowing of

foreign words in the Chinese language is a rare phenomenon as Chinese has intrinsic resistance to such kind of borrowing.

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